

Satellite Data (NRSC)

SPOT IMAGE

Scene Parameters

Part 1 of 3

CST 551
August 1996

Produced at Manchester Computing in accordance with an agreement between the Combined Higher Education Software Team (CHEST) and National Remote Sensing Centre Ltd. (NRSC)/SPOT IMAGE.

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Preface to the Manchester Reprint

This document is a straight reprint of the manual produced by National Remote Sensing Centre Ltd. (NRSC) and SPOT IMAGE.

We are grateful to NRSC and SPOT IMAGE for permission to reproduce this manual for the higher education and research community in the U.K.

Reprinted at Manchester Computing, University of Manchester.

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PART 1

CD-ROM Directories

In order of appearance

CD Number : 700006014
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 30-JUN-1995 12:04:06

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 022-243 89/02/20 11:57:30 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	02	Scene std.	1 022-244 89/12/04 11:38:58 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	03	Scene std.	2 022-245 95/03/24 11:56:54 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	04	Scene std.	1 024-246 89/07/16 11:50:17 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	05	Scene std.	1 026-247 88/05/22 11:26:24 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	06	Scene std.	1 028-246 88/05/17 11:22:18 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	07	Scene std.	1 029-241 87/01/31 10:59:17 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	08	Scene std.	1 029-242 87/04/24 11:02:42 1 P Level 1B SAT 0 No Q/L
9	09	Scene std.	1 029-244 88/05/17 11:22:02 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	10	Scene std.	1 029-245 88/05/17 11:22:10 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 700006013
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 30-JUN-1995 11:15:11

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	11	Scene std.	1 032-246 89/01/22 11:15:26 2 P Level 1B SAT 0 x
2	12	Scene std.	1 034-245 88/12/12 11:03:48 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	13	Scene std.	1 022-244 90/07/31 11:42:55 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	14	Scene std.	1 022-248 90/09/10 11:55:08 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	15	Scene std.	2 025-241 90/07/24 11:27:13 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	16	Scene std.	2 025-242 90/07/24 11:27:21 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	17	Scene std.	2 025-243 91/01/23 11:08:07 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	18	Scene std.	1 025-244 89/07/16 11:50:00 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	19	Scene std.	2 025-245 90/12/05 11:51:07 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	20	Scene std.	2 025-247 90/09/10 11:04:53 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005745
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:02:57

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	30	Scene std.	2 026-246 93/03/13 11:10:10 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	26	Scene std.	2 026-243 93/03/13 11:09:44 2 P Level 1B SAT 0 02
3	29	Scene std.	2 026-245 93/03/13 11:10:02 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	27	Scene std.	2 026-244 93/03/13 11:09:54 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	25	Scene std.	2 026-243 93/03/13 11:09:46 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	24	Scene std.	2 026-242 93/03/13 11:09:36 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	23	Scene std.	2 026-242 91/09/03 11:19:57 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	21	Scene std.	2 025-248 90/09/10 11:05:01 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	28	Scene std.	2 026-244 93/03/13 11:09:53 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	22	Scene std.	2 026-241 91/11/09 11:31:34 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005758
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 15-JUN-1995 09:27:40

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	31	Scene std.	2 026-248 91/03/25 11:35:24 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	32	Scene std.	2 028-246 93/03/13 11:10:09 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	33	Scene std.	1 028-247 92/05/22 11:40:50 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
→ 4	34	Scene std.	2 029-241 90/12/01 11:27:24 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	35	Scene std.	2 029-243 93/02/05 11:02:08 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	36	Scene std.	2 029-245 93/03/13 11:10:01 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	37	Scene std.	2 030-242 91/11/26 11:04:38 1 P Level 1B SAT 1
8	38	Scene std.	3 030-243 94/03/14 11:27:07 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	39	Scene std.	2 030-244 94/03/26 11:38:29 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	40	Scene std.	2 030-245 90/07/13 11:39:07 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005760
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:01:26

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	41	Scene std.	2 030-246 94/03/26 11:38:46 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	42	Scene std.	2 030-247 94/03/26 11:38:54 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	43	Scene std.	2 032-246 91/09/13 11:28:08 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	44	Scene std.	2 032-247 91/09/13 11:28:16 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	45	Scene std.	2 033-243 91/09/13 11:27:43 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	46	Scene std.	2 033-244 94/01/14 11:03:24 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	47	Scene std.	3 033-244 94/01/17 11:03:56 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	48	Scene std.	3 033-245 94/02/06 11:19:32 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	49	Scene std.	2 034-243 90/08/03 11:35:03 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	50	Scene std.	3 034-244 94/01/16 11:23:12 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

CD Number : 7000005704
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 8-JUN-1995 11:42:27

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	53	Scene std.	2 021-242 93/02/14 11:29:09 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	51	Scene std.	2 034-246 91/01/07 11:16:17 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	52	Scene std.	3 034-247 94/01/16 11:23:36 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 3

PART 1

CD Number : 7000006014
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 30-JUN-1995 12:04:06

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	01	Scene std.	1 022-243 89/02/20 11:57:30 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	02	Scene std.	1 022-244 89/12/04 11:38:58 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	03	Scene std.	2 022-245 95/03/24 11:56:54 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	04	Scene std.	1 024-246 89/07/16 11:50:17 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	05	Scene std.	1 026-247 88/05/22 11:26:24 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	06	Scene std.	1 028-246 88/05/17 11:22:18 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	07	Scene std.	1 029-241 87/01/31 10:59:17 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	08	Scene std.	1 029-242 87/04/24 11:02:42 1 P Level 1B SAT 0 No Q/L
9	09	Scene std.	1 029-244 88/05/17 11:22:02 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	10	Scene std.	1 029-245 88/05/17 11:22:10 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505232601
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 22-243 89/02/20 11:57:30 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:38:54

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 22-243 89/02/20 11:57:30 2 P
K-J identification 22-243
Date 89/02/20
Time 11 h 57 mn 30 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 019.4 Degres
Incidence angle L27.5 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +170.5 Elevation: 025.6
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.93956

Number of lines 6013
Number of pixels per line 7728
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'15"
Longitude W004°36'07"
Pixel number 3787
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°04'53"	W004°57'20"	219	1
2	N052°51'21"	W003°54'08"	7728	1
3	N052°34'37"	W005°16'33"	1	6013
4	N052°21'16"	W004°13'59"	7510	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232602
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 22-244 89/12/04 11:38:58 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:36:04

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 22-244 89/12/04 11:38:58 1 P
K-J identification 22-244
Date 89/12/04
Time 11 h 38 mn 58 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.8 Degres
Incidence angle L09.3 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +173.5 Elevation: 015.5
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94008

Number of lines 6008
Number of pixels per line 6385
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'08"
Longitude W004°02'06"
Pixel number 3172
Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°35'00"	W004°19'49"	241	1
2	N052°25'54"	W003°27'37"	6385	1
3	N052°04'08"	W004°35'58"	1	6008
4	N051°55'09"	W003°44'19"	6145	6008

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6009	6008
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232603
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 2 22-245 95/03/24 11:56:54 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:41:03

S P O T

 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 22-245 95/03/24 11:56:54 2 P
K-J Identification 22-245
Date 95/03/24
Time 11 h 56 mn 54 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 019.5 Degres
Incidence angle L30.3 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +171.1 Elevation: 038.9
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.52179

Number of lines 6013
Number of pixels per line 8130
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'59"
Longitude W004°27'49"
Pixel number 3973
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°08'59"	W004°50'00"	225	1
2	N051°54'39"	W003°44'55"	8130	1
3	N051°38'44"	W005°08'59"	1	6013
4	N051°24'36"	W004°04'32"	7906	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232604
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 24-246 89/07/16 11:50:17 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:40:17

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 24-246 89/07/16 11:50:17 2 P
K-J identification 24-246
Date 89/07/16
Time 11 h 50 mn 17 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 018.3 Degres
Incidence angle L25.4 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +165.4 Elevation: 059.7
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.92441

Number of lines 6014
Number of pixels per line 7484
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'44"
Longitude W004°01'47"
Pixel number 3674
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°39'56"	W004°21'57"	229	1
2	N051°27'33"	W003°22'25"	7484	1
3	N051°09'28"	W004°39'48"	1	6014
4	N050°57'15"	W003°40'51"	7256	6014

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6015	6014
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232605
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 26-247 88/05/22 11:26:24 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:52:32

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 26-247 88/05/22 11:26:24 1 P
K-J identification 26-247
Date 88/05/22
Time 11 h 26 mn 24 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.2 Degres
Incidence angle L01.9 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +160.4 Elevation: 058.4
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.97559

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6252
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°50'28"
Longitude W003°15'08"
Pixel number 3121
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°09'55"	W003°32'41"	257	1
2	N051°01'58"	W002°42'55"	6252	1
3	N050°38'49"	W003°47'02"	1	6004
4	N050°30'57"	W002°57'48"	5996	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232606
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 28-246 88/05/17 11:22:18 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:48:42

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 28-246 88/05/17 11:22:18 2 P
K-J Identification 28-246
Date 88/05/17
Time 11 h 22 mn 18 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.4 Degres
Incidence angle L02.2 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +161.7 Elevation: 057.0
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.95471

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6252
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'44"
Longitude W001°58'38"
Pixel number 3121
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°38'14"	W002°16'16"	251	1
2	N051°30'09"	W001°26'00"	6252	1
3	N051°07'10"	W002°30'56"	1	6004
4	N050°59'10"	W001°41'11"	6002	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232607
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 29-241 87/01/31 10:59:17 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:53:30

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 29-241 87/01/31 10:59:17 1 P
K-J identification 29-241
Date 87/01/31
Time 10 h 59 mn 17 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 010.5 Degres
Incidence angle R24.1 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +161.0 Elevation: 017.0
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.99588

Number of lines 5976
Number of pixels per line 7376
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'17"
Longitude W000°33'22"
Pixel number 3749
Line number 2986

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°58'29"	W000°59'45"	263	1
2	N053°51'29"	E000°04'06"	7376	1
3	N053°27'02"	W001°11'33"	1	5976
4	N053°20'06"	W000°08'29"	7114	5976

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5977	5976
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232608
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 29-242 87/04/24 11:02:42 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:53:36

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 29-242 87/04/24 11:02:42 1 P
K-J Identification 29-242
Date 87/04/24
Time 11 h 02 mn 42 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track
Processing level 1A
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 011.2 Degres
Incidence angle R20.0 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +158.5 Elevation: 047.8
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.99588

Number of lines 6000
Number of pixels per line 6000
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'18"
Longitude W000°43'16"
Pixel number 3000
Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°31'48"	W001°05'43"	1	1
2	N053°24'23"	W000°09'24"	6000	1
3	N052°58'09"	W001°17'39"	1	6000
4	N052°50'49"	W000°22'01"	6000	6000

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6001	6000
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232609
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 29-244 88/05/17 11:22:02 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 11:02:14

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 29-244 88/05/17 11:22:02 2 P
K-J identification 29-244
Date 88/05/17
Time 11 h 22 mn 02 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.7 Degres
Incidence angle L02.2 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +162.8 Elevation: 056.2
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.95471

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6248
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'08"
Longitude W001°31'00"
Pixel number 3118
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°34'42"	W001°48'52"	245	1
2	N052°26'26"	W000°57'35"	6248	1
3	N052°03'40"	W002°04'03"	1	6004
4	N051°55'30"	W001°13'20"	6004	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232610
CD number : 7000006014
Scene ID : 1 29-245 88/05/17 11:22:10 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:59:19

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 29-245 88/05/17 11:22:10 2 P
K-J identification 29-245
Date 88/05/17
Time 11 h 22 mn 10 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.6 Degres
Incidence angle 102.2 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +162.2 Elevation: 056.6
Gain Number 5
Absolute callbration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.95471

Number of lines 6004
Number of pixels per line 6249
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'58"
Longitude W001°44'56"
Pixel number 3120
Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°06'30"	W002°02'41"	247	1
2	N051°58'19"	W001°11'55"	6249	1
3	N051°35'27"	W002°17'36"	1	6004
4	N051°27'22"	W001°27'22"	6003	6004

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6005	6004
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT1 HRV2 022-243/0 20 FEB 89
P

N52°43' / W084°36' 27°L 11H 57MN 31S N1B
BMA07048 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

BMA07048

SPOT1 HRV1 022-244/0 04 DEC 89
P

NS2°15'W004°02' 09°L 11H 38MN 59S N1B
BMA07049 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

BMA07049

SPOT2 HRV2 022-245/0 24 MAR 95
P

N51°47'W084°28' 38°L 11H 56MN 545 N18
BMA10898 CCTCONTROL @CNES1995

BMA10898

SPOT1 HRV2 024-246/0 16 JUL 89
P

N51°19'W004°02' 25°L 11H 50MN 17S N18
BMA07051 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

SPOT 1 HRV 1 026-247 22 MAY 88
P

N50°50' W003°15' 01"L 11H 26MN 24S N1B
ST042223 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BMA 07602

SPOT1 HRV2 028-246/0 17 MAY 88
P

N51°19' / W001°59' 02"L 11H 22MN 185 N1B
52418012 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BNA 01237

61A 5123

SPOT 1 HRV 1 029-241 31 JAN 87
P

N53°39' W000°33' 24"R 10H 59MN 17S N1E
ST028065 CCTCONTROL @CHES1987

SPOT1 HRV2 029-244/0 17 MAY 88
P

N52°15'W001°31' 02°L 11H 22MN 025 N1B
BMA09221 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BMA09221

SPOT 1 HRV 2 029-245 17 MAY 88
P

N51°47'W001°45' 02°L 11H 22MN 10S N1B
ST042282 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BMA07603

CD Number : 700006013
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 30-JUN-1995 11:15:11

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	11	Scene std.	1 032-246 89/01/22 11:15:26 2 P Level 1B SAT 0 x
2	12	Scene std.	1 034-245 88/12/12 11:03:48 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	13	Scene std.	1 022-244 90/07/31 11:42:55 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	14	Scene std.	1 022-248 90/09/10 11:55:08 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	15	Scene std.	2 025-241 90/07/24 11:27:13 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	16	Scene std.	2 025-242 90/07/24 11:27:21 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	17	Scene std.	2 025-243 91/01/23 11:08:07 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	18	Scene std.	1 025-244 89/07/16 11:50:00 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	19	Scene std.	2 025-245 90/12/05 11:51:07 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	20	Scene std.	2 025-247 90/09/10 11:04:53 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505232611
 CD number : 7000006013
 Scene ID : 1 32-246 89/01/22 11:15:26 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:42:38

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 32-246 89/01/22 11:15:26 2 P
 K-J identification 32-246
 Date 89/01/22
 Time 11 h 15 mn 26 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1A
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 014.4 Degres
 Incidence angle L02.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +166.1 Elevation: 018.0
 Gain Number 5
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94798

Number of lines 6000
 Number of pixels per line 6000
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'44"
 Longitude W000°03'54"
 Pixel number 3000
 Line number 3000

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°38'39"	W000°21'58"	1	1
2	N051°29'55"	E000°28'05"	6000	1
3	N051°07'24"	W000°35'33"	1	6000
4	N050°58'46"	E000°13'58"	6000	6000

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6001	6000
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232612
CD number : 7000006013
Scene ID : 1 34-245 88/12/12 11:03:48 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:32:42

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 34-245 88/12/12 11:03:48 1 P
K-J identification 34-245
Date 88/12/12
Time 11 h 03 mn 48 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 012.8 Degres
Incidence angle R08.4 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +169.1 Elevation: 014.6
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.96883

Number of lines 5995
Number of pixels per line 6377
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'58"
Longitude E001°01'35"
Pixel number 3204
Line number 2996

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°06'13"	E000°42'15"	261	1
2	N051°58'52"	E001°34'23"	6377	1
3	N051°34'58"	E000°28'47"	1	5995
4	N051°27'42"	E001°20'21"	6117	5995

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5996	5995
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232613
CD number : 700006013
Scene ID : 1 22-244 90/07/31 11:42:55 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:36:37

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 22-244 90/07/31 11:42:55 2 P
K-J identification 22-244
Date 90/07/31
Time 11 h 42 mn 55 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.3 Degres
Incidence angle L11.7 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +162.5 Elevation: 055.5
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.91430

Number of lines 6010
Number of pixels per line 6471
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'08"
Longitude W004°31'19"
Pixel number 3210
Line number 3004

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°35'09"	W004°49'09"	237	1
2	N052°25'40"	W003°56'18"	6471	1
3	N052°04'21"	W005°05'39"	1	6010
4	N051°54'59"	W004°13'21"	6235	6010

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6011	6010
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232614
CD number : 7000006013
Scene ID : 1 22-248 90/09/10 11:55:08 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:33:45

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 22-248 90/09/10 11:55:08 1 P
K-J identification 22-248
Date 90/09/10
Time 11 h 55 mn 08 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 017.9 Degres
Incidence angle L25.8 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +171.6 Elevation: 044.6
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.94008

Number of lines 6011
Number of pixels per line 7536
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°22'07"
Longitude W005°28'29"
Pixel number 3698
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N050°43'15"	W005°48'37"	237	1
2	N050°31'04"	W004°49'47"	7536	1
3	N050°12'44"	W006°05'51"	1	6011
4	N050°00'41"	W005°07'34"	7300	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232615
CD number : 700006013
Scene ID : 2 25-241 90/07/24 11:27:13 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:45:01

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 25-241 90/07/24 11:27:13 1 P
K-J identification 25-241
Date 90/07/24
Time 11 h 27 mn 13 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.3 Degres
Incidence angle R03.0 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +159.0 Elevation: 055.2
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 6000
Number of pixels per line 6255
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'00"
Longitude W002°50'34"
Pixel number 3133
Line number 2999

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°58'29"	W003°09'25"	243	1
2	N053°50'25"	W002°16'15"	6255	1
3	N053°27'25"	W003°24'41"	1	6000
4	N053°19'28"	W002°32'08"	6013	6000

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6001	6000
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232616
CD number : 7000006013
Scene ID : 2 25-242 90/07/24 11:27:21 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:49:18

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 25-242 90/07/24 11:27:21 1 P
K-J identification 25-242
Date 90/07/24
Time 11 h 27 mn 21 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 014.2 Degres
Incidence angle R03.0 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +158.4 Elevation: 055.6
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 6000
Number of pixels per line 6257
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'00"
Longitude W003°04'30"
Pixel number 3135
Line number 2999

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°30'27"	W003°23'12"	245	1
2	N053°22'29"	W002°30'36"	6257	1
3	N052°59'22"	W003°38'12"	1	6000
4	N052°51'30"	W002°46'11"	6013	6000

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6001	6000
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232617
CD number : 7000006013
Scene ID : 2 25-243 91/01/23 11:08:07 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:47:21

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 25-243 91/01/23 11:08:07 2 P
K-J Identification 25-243
Date 91/01/23
Time 11 h 08 mn 07 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 009.8 Degres
Incidence angle R26.5 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +161.1 Elevation: 016.0
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65076

Number of lines 5973
Number of pixels per line 7658
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'15"
Longitude W003°22'26"
Pixel number 3900
Line number 2984

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°02'24"	W003°49'52"	271	1
2	N052°55'33"	W002°44'51"	7658	1
3	N052°30'53"	W004°00'54"	1	5973
4	N052°24'07"	W002°56'40"	7388	5973

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5974	5973
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232618
CD number : 7000006013
Scene ID : 1 25-244 89/07/16 11:50:00 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 10:21:23

S P O T

 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 25-244 89/07/16 11:50:00 2 P
K-J identification 25-244
Date 89/07/16
Time 11 h 50 mn 00 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 018.8 Degres
Incidence angle L25.4 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.7 Elevation: 058.9
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.92441

Number of lines 6014
Number of pixels per line 7480
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'08"
Longitude W003°27'26"
Pixel number 3672
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°36'26"	W003°47'47"	223	1
2	N052°23'46"	W002°47'08"	7480	1
3	N052°06'03"	W004°06'21"	1	6014
4	N051°53'32"	W003°06'18"	7258	6014

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6015	6014
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232619
CD number : 7000006013
Scene ID : 2 25-245 90/12/05 11:51:07 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:57:06

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 25-245 90/12/05 11:51:07 1 P
K-J identification 25-245
Date 90/12/05
Time 11 h 51 mn 07 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 018.4 Degres
Incidence angle L25.1 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +176.5 Elevation: 016.0
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.78691

Number of lines 6012
Number of pixels per line 7450
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'58"
Longitude W003°50'10"
Pixel number 3658
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°08'09"	W004°10'22"	229	1
2	N051°55'46"	W003°10'31"	7450	1
3	N051°37'43"	W004°28'28"	1	6012
4	N051°25'29"	W003°29'13"	7222	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232620
CD number : 7000006013
Scene ID : 2 25-247 90/09/10 11:04:53 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 30-JUN-1995 09:57:30

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 25-247 90/09/10 11:04:53 1 P
K-J Identification 25-247
Date 90/09/10
Time 11 h 04 mn 53 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 008.7 Degres
Incidence angle R31.1 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +156.6 Elevation: 042.2
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 5966
Number of pixels per line 8290
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°50'28"
Longitude W004°06'22"
Pixel number 4239
Line number 2980

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°09'31"	W004°36'02"	283	1
2	N051°02'57"	W003°28'15"	8290	1
3	N050°37'56"	W004°45'44"	1	5966
4	N050°31'25"	W003°38'43"	8008	5966

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5967	5966
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT1 HRV1 034-245/0 12 DEC 88
P

NS1°47' / E001°02' 00°R 11H 03M 48S N1B
BMA07052 CCTCONTROL @CNES1988

BMA07052

SPOT1 HRV2 022-244/0 31 JUL 90
P'

N52°15'W004°31' 11°L 11H 42MN 56S N1B
BMA07053 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA07053

SPOT1 HRV1 022-248/0 10 SEP 90
P

N50°22' / W005°28' 25°L 11H 53MN 09S N18
BMA07054 CCTCONTROL @CHES1990

BMA 07054

SPOT2 HRV1 025-241/0 24 JUL 90
P

N53°39' / W002°51' 02"R 11H 27MN 14S N1B
BMA07055 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA07055

SPOT2 HRV1 025-242/0 24 JUL 90
P

N53°11' W083°04' 02°R 11H 27MN 21S N1B
BMA09392 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA09392

SPOT2 HRV2 025-243/0 23 JAN 91
P

N52°43' / W003°22' 26°R 11H 08MN 075 N18
BMA07056 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA 07056

SPOT1 HRV2 025-244/0 16 JUL 89
P

NS2°15'W003°27' 25°L 11H 50M 00S N1B
BMA10922 CCTCONTROL @CNES1989

BMA10922

SPOT2 HRV1 025-245/0 05 DEC 90
P

N51°47' / W003°50' 25°L 11H 51MN 07S N1B
BMA02237 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA 2237

SPOT2 HRV1 025-247/0 10 SEP 90
P

N50°50' / W004°06' 31°R 11H 04MN 53S N1B
BMA05703 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA05703

CD Number : 7000005745
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:02:57

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	30	Scene std.	2 026-246 93/03/13 11:10:10 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	26	Scene std.	2 026-243 93/03/13 11:09:44 2 P Level 1B SAT 0 ✗
3	29	Scene std.	2 026-245 93/03/13 11:10:02 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	27	Scene std.	2 026-244 93/03/13 11:09:54 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	25	Scene std.	2 026-243 93/03/13 11:09:46 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	24	Scene std.	2 026-242 93/03/13 11:09:36 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	23	Scene std.	2 026-242 91/09/03 11:19:57 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	21	Scene std.	2 025-248 90/09/10 11:05:01 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	28	Scene std.	2 026-244 93/03/13 11:09:53 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	22	Scene std.	2 026-241 91/11/09 11:31:34 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505232630
CD number : 7000005745
Scene ID : 2 26-246 93/03/13 11:10:10 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 14:06:30

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-246 93/03/13 11:10:10 1 P
K-J identification 26-246
Date 93/03/13
Time 11 h 10 mn 10 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 010.2 Degres
Incidence angle R23.4 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +158.2 Elevation: 033.1
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.69365

Number of lines 5979
Number of pixels per line 7314
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'46"
Longitude W003°13'08"
Pixel number 3715
Line number 2987

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°37'51"	W003°37'54"	275	1
2	N051°31'07"	W002°37'58"	7314	1
3	N051°06'21"	W003°48'59"	1	5979
4	N050°59'41"	W002°49'42"	7040	5979

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5980	5979
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232626
CD number : 7000005745
Scene ID : 2 26-243 93/03/13 11:09:44 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 13:58:28

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-243 93/03/13 11:09:44 2 P
K-J identification 26-243
Date 93/03/13
Time 11 h 09 mn 44 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 011.1 Degres
Incidence angle R19.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +160.0 Elevation: 032.1
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.57911

Number of lines 5983
Number of pixels per line 6972
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'16"
Longitude W001°51'17"
Pixel number 3533
Line number 2990

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°02'27"	W002°14'48"	265	1
2	N052°55'26"	W001°16'02"	6972	1
3	N052°31'02"	W002°27'00"	1	5983
4	N052°24'06"	W001°28'55"	6708	5983

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5984	5983
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232629
CD number : 7000005745
Scene ID : 2 26-245 93/03/13 11:10:02 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 14:05:50

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-245 93/03/13 11:10:02 1 P
K-J Identification 26-245
Date 93/03/13
Time 11 h 10 mn 02 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 010.3 Degres
Incidence angle R23.4 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +158.4 Elevation: 032.7
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.69365

Number of lines 5979
Number of pixels per line 7313
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°47'00"
Longitude W003°02'49"
Pixel number 3714
Line number 2987

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°06'06"	W003°27'49"	273	1
2	N051°59'19"	W002°27'16"	7313	1
3	N051°34'37"	W003°39'03"	1	5979
4	N051°27'53"	W002°39'11"	7041	5979

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5980	5979
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232627
 CD number : 7000005745
 Scene ID : 2 26-244 93/03/13 11:09:54 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 13:57:28

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-244 93/03/13 11:09:54 1 P
 K-J identification 26-244
 Date 93/03/13
 Time 11 h 09 mn 54 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.4 Degres
 Incidence angle R23.4 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +158.7 Elevation: 032.3
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.69365

Number of lines 5978
 Number of pixels per line 7309
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'09"
 Longitude W002°52'22"
 Pixel number 3714
 Line number 2987

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°34'17"	W003°17'37"	269	1
2	N052°27'26"	W002°16'25"	7309	1
3	N052°02'49"	W003°29'00"	1	5978
4	N051°56'02"	W002°28'31"	7041	5978

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5979	5978
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232625
CD number : 7000005745
Scene ID : 2 26-243 93/03/13 11:09:46 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 12:51:05

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-243 93/03/13 11:09:46 1 P
K-J identification 26-243
Date 93/03/13
Time 11 h 09 mn 46 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 010.4 Degres
Incidence angle R23.4 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +159.0 Elevation: 031.9
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.69365

Number of lines 5978
Number of pixels per line 7308
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'16"
Longitude W002°41'46"
Pixel number 3713
Line number 2987

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°02'25"	W003°07'15"	267	1
2	N052°55'31"	W002°05'25"	7308	1
3	N052°30'57"	W003°18'50"	1	5978
4	N052°24'07"	W002°17'42"	7042	5978

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5979	5978
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232624
CD number : 7000005745
Scene ID : 2 26-242 93/03/13 11:09:36 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 13:56:40

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-242 93/03/13 11:09:36 2 P
K-J identification 26-242
Date 93/03/13
Time 11 h 09 mn 36 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 011.2 Degres
Incidence angle R19.6 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +160.2 Elevation: 031.7
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.57911

Number of lines 5983
Number of pixels per line 6971
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'19"
Longitude W001°39'58"
Pixel number 3531
Line number 2990

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°30'31"	W002°03'43"	263	1
2	N053°23'27"	W001°04'18"	6971	1
3	N052°59'07"	W002°16'07"	1	5983
4	N052°52'07"	W001°17'24"	6709	5983

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5984	5983
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232623
 CD number : 7000005745
 Scene ID : 2 26-242 91/09/03 11:19:57 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 12:46:50

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-242 91/09/03 11:19:57 1 P
 K-J identification 26-242
 Date 91/09/03
 Time 11 h 19 mn 57 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 013.4 Degres
 Incidence angle R07.7 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +163.5 Elevation: 043.7
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.35460

Number of lines 5996
 Number of pixels per line 6348
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'18"
 Longitude W002°03'06"
 Pixel number 3191
 Line number 2996

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°30'39"	W002°22'43"	249	1
2	N053°23'01"	W001°29'09"	6348	1
3	N052°59'29"	W002°37'01"	1	5996
4	N052°51'56"	W001°44'04"	6100	5996

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5997	5996
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232621
CD number : 7000005745
Scene ID : 2 25-248 90/09/10 11:05:01 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 14:08:37

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 25-248 90/09/10 11:05:01 1 P
K-J identification 25-248
Date 90/09/10
Time 11 h 05 mn 01 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 008.7 Degres
Incidence angle R31.1 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +156.2 Elevation: 042.6
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.37760

Number of lines 5966
Number of pixels per line 8293
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°22'07"
Longitude W004°15'22"
Pixel number 4240
Line number 2980

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N050°41'10"	W004°44'45"	287	1
2	N050°34'38"	W003°37'39"	8293	1
3	N050°09'34"	W004°54'20"	1	5966
4	N050°03'05"	W003°47'58"	8007	5966

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5967	5966
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232628
CD number : 7000005745
Scene ID : 2 26-244 93/03/13 11:09:53 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 13:58:55

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-244 93/03/13 11:09:53 2 P
K-J identification 26-244
Date 93/03/13
Time 11 h 09 mn 53 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 011.0 Degres
Incidence angle R19.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +159.7 Elevation: 032.5
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.57911

Number of lines 5984
Number of pixels per line 6976
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'10"
Longitude W002°02'26"
Pixel number 3533
Line number 2990

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°34'18"	W002°25'45"	269	1
2	N052°27'22"	W001°27'35"	6976	1
3	N052°02'53"	W002°37'45"	1	5984
4	N051°56'01"	W001°40'15"	6708	5984

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5985	5984
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232622
 CD number : 7000005745
 Scene ID : 2 26-241 91/11/09 11:31:34 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 12:48:20

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-241 91/11/09 11:31:34 2 P
 K-J identification 26-241
 Date 91/11/09
 Time 11 h 31 mn 34 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.9 Degres
 Incidence angle L06.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +174.9 Elevation: 019.6
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.64216

Number of lines 6006
 Number of pixels per line 6305
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'17"
 Longitude W001°54'27"
 Pixel number 3139
 Line number 3002

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°59'06"	W002°12'30"	235	1
2	N053°50'06"	W001°19'14"	6305	1
3	N053°28'15"	W002°29'09"	1	6006
4	N053°19'22"	W001°36'28"	6071	6006

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6007	6006
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT2 HRV1 026-246/0 13 MAR 93
P

NS1°19'W003°13' 23°R 11H 10MN 10S N1B
BMA07071 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA07071

SPOT2 HRV1 026-243/0 13 MAR 93
P

N52°43'W002°42' 23°R 11H 09MN 465 N1B
BMA07061 CCTCONTROL 0CNES1993

BMA 07061

SPOT2 HRV1 026-245/0 13 MAR 93
P

NS1°47'10.003"03' 23°R 11H 10MN 02S N1B
BMA07069 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA 07069

SPOT2 HRV2 026-244/0 13 MAR 93
P

N52°15' / W002°02' 19°R 11H 09MN 535 N1B
BMA07068 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA 07068

SPOT2 HRV2 026-243/0 13 MAR 93
P

N52°43'W001°51' 19°R 11H 09MN 44S N1B
BMA07062 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA07062

SPOT2 HRV2 026-242/0 13 MAR 93
P

N53°11' W001°40' 19°R 11H 09MN 36S N1B
BMA07060 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA07060

SPOT2 HRY1 026-242/0 03 SEP 91
P

N53°11'40.02"03' 07°R 11H 19MN 57S N1B
BMA07059 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA04059

SPOT2 HRV1 025-248/0 10 SEP 90
P

N50°22' / W004°15' 31°R 11H 05MN 01S N18
BMA05144 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA 05244

SPOT2 HRV1 026-244/0 13 MAR 93
P

N52°15' / W002°52' 23°R 11H 09MN 54S N1B
BMA07065 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA 07065

SPOT2 HRV2 026-241/0 09 NOV 91
P

N53°39'00" S 01°54'06" L 11H 31MN 34S N1B
BMA07058 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07058

CD Number : 7000005758
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 15-JUN-1995 09:27:40

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	31	Scene std.	2 026-248 91/03/25 11:35:24 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	32	Scene std.	2 028-246 93/03/13 11:10:09 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	33	Scene std.	1 028-247 92/05/22 11:40:50 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
→ 4	34	Scene std.	2 029-241 90/12/01 11:27:24 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	35	Scene std.	2 029-243 93/02/05 11:02:08 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	36	Scene std.	2 029-245 93/03/13 11:10:01 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	37	Scene std.	2 030-242 91/11/26 11:04:38 1 P Level 1B SAT 1
8	38	Scene std.	3 030-243 94/03/14 11:27:07 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	39	Scene std.	2 030-244 94/03/26 11:38:29 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	40	Scene std.	2 030-245 90/07/13 11:39:07 2 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505232631
 CD number : 7000005758
 Scene ID : 2 26-248 91/03/25 11:35:24 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:52:01

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 26-248 91/03/25 11:35:24 2 P
 K-J identification 26-248
 Date 91/03/25
 Time 11 h 35 mn 24 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.3 Degres
 Incidence angle L10.4 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +164.8 Elevation: 040.0
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65076

Number of lines 6008
 Number of pixels per line 6436
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°22'07"
 Longitude W003°48'46"
 Pixel number 3196
 Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N050°41'54"	W004°06'10"	251	1
2	N050°33'04"	W003°15'37"	6436	1
3	N050°10'58"	W004°21'18"	1	6008
4	N050°02'13"	W003°31'15"	6186	6008

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6009	6008
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232632
CD number : 7000005758
Scene ID : 2 28-246 93/03/13 11:10:09 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:54:04

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 28-246 93/03/13 11:10:09 2 P
K-J identification 28-246
Date 93/03/13
Time 11 h 10 mn 09 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 010.8 Degres
Incidence angle R19.6 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +159.1 Elevation: 033.3
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.57911

Number of lines 5984
Number of pixels per line 6978
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'46"
Longitude W002°24'16"
Pixel number 3536
Line number 2990

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°37'52"	W002°47'10"	273	1
2	N051°31'03"	W001°50'11"	6978	1
3	N051°06'25"	W002°58'49"	1	5984
4	N050°59'40"	W002°02'28"	6706	5984

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5985	5984
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232633
CD number : 7000005758
Scene ID : 1 28-247 92/05/22 11:40:50 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:14:17

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 1 28-247 92/05/22 11:40:50 1 P
K-J identification 28-247
Date 92/05/22
Time 11 h 40 mn 50 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 018.1 Degres
Incidence angle L25.8 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +168.6 Elevation: 059.2
Gain Number 5
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 00.90965

Number of lines 6011
Number of pixels per line 7534
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°50'29"
Longitude W002°17'33"
Pixel number 3698
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°11'39"	W002°37'47"	235	1
2	N050°59'20"	W001°38'25"	7534	1
3	N050°41'10"	W002°55'19"	1	6011
4	N050°29'00"	W001°56'31"	7300	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232634
 CD number : 7000005758
 Scene ID : 2 29-241 90/12/01 11:27:24 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:16:59

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 29-241 90/12/01 11:27:24 2 P
 K-J identification 29-241
 Date 90/12/01
 Time 11 h 27 mn 24 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.6 Degres
 Incidence angle L04.9 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +173.6 Elevation: 014.6
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65649

Number of lines 6005
 Number of pixels per line 6281
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°39'17"
 Longitude W001°15'40"
 Pixel number 3129
 Line number 3001

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°59'02"	W001°33'46"	237	1
2	N053°50'13"	W000°40'39"	6281	1
3	N053°28'10"	W001°50'12"	1	6005
4	N053°19'27"	W000°57'41"	6045	6005

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6006	6005
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232635
 CD number : 7000005758
 Scene ID : 2 29-243 93/02/05 11:02:08 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:14:45

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 29-243 93/02/05 11:02:08 2 P
 K-J identification 29-243
 Date 93/02/05
 Time 11 h 02 mn 08 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.1 Degres
 Incidence angle R25.1 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +160.6 Elevation: 019.3
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.71424

Number of lines 5975
 Number of pixels per line 7497
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record. byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'16"
 Longitude W001°07'42"
 Pixel number 3815
 Line number 2985

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°02'25"	W001°34'14"	269	1
2	N052°55'33"	W000°30'41"	7497	1
3	N052°30'56"	W001°45'31"	1	5975
4	N052°24'08"	W000°42'43"	7229	5975

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5976	5975
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232636
 CD number : 7000005758
 Scene ID : 2 29-245 93/03/13 11:10:01 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:17:29

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 29-245 93/03/13 11:10:01 2 P
 K-J identification 29-245
 Date 93/03/13
 Time 11 h 10 mn 01 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 010.9 Degres
 Incidence angle R19.6 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +159.4 Elevation: 032.9
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.57911

Number of lines 5984
 Number of pixels per line 6977
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'59"
 Longitude W002°13'25"
 Pixel number 3534
 Line number 2990

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°06'07"	W002°36'32"	271	1
2	N051°59'14"	W001°38'58"	6977	1
3	N051°34'40"	W002°48'21"	1	5984
4	N051°27'52"	W001°51'26"	6707	5984

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5985	5984
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232637
 CD number : 7000005758
 Scene ID : 2 30-242 91/11/26 11:04:38 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:27:12

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 30-242 91/11/26 11:04:38 1 P
 K-J identification 30-242
 Date 91/11/26
 Time 11 h 04 mn 38 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 1
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 011.7 Degres
 Incidence angle R17.2 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +169.5 Elevation: 015.6
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.75707

Number of lines 5985
 Number of pixels per line 6797
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°08'11"
 Longitude W000°09'47"
 Pixel number 3437
 Line number 2991

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°27'24"	W000°32'27"	259	1
2	N053°20'14"	E000°25'17"	6797	1
3	N052°56'03"	W000°45'14"	1	5985
4	N052°48'58"	E000°11'50"	6539	5985

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5986	5985
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232638
 CD number : 7000005758
 Scene ID : 3 30-243 94/03/14 11:27:07 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:29:09

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 30-243 94/03/14 11:27:07 2 P
 K-J identification 30-243
 Date 94/03/14
 Time 11 h 27 mn 07 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 016.4 Degres
 Incidence angle L11.7 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.8 Elevation: 033.5
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.61395

Number of lines 6009
 Number of pixels per line 6482
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'16"
 Longitude W000°21'36"
 Pixel number 3215
 Line number 3004

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°03'18"	W000°39'35"	241	1
2	N052°53'46"	E000°13'52"	6482	1
3	N052°32'32"	W000°56'23"	1	6009
4	N052°23'07"	W000°03'30"	6242	6009

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6010	6009
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232639
CD number : 7000005758
Scene ID : 2 30-244 94/03/26 11:38:29 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:27:50

S P O T

 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 30-244 94/03/26 11:38:29 2 P
K-J identification 30-244
Date 94/03/26
Time 11 h 38 mn 29 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 018.6 Degres
Incidence angle L24.8 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +170.2 Elevation: 039.1
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.53899

Number of lines 6013
Number of pixels per line 7414
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'10"
Longitude W000°41'02"
Pixel number 3642
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°36'22"	W001°01'13"	227	1
2	N052°23'56"	W000°01'05"	7414	1
3	N052°05'57"	W001°19'39"	1	6013
4	N051°53'40"	W000°20'06"	7188	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232640
 CD number : 7000005758
 Scene ID : 2 30-245 90/07/13 11:39:07 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:29:50

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 30-245 90/07/13 11:39:07 2 P
 K-J identification 30-245
 Date 90/07/13
 Time 11 h 39 mn 07 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 018.5 Degres
 Incidence angle L25.5 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.4 Elevation: 059.8
 Gain Number 6
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.27814

Number of lines 6012
 Number of pixels per line 7497
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'43"
 Longitude W000°48'42"
 Pixel number 3680
 Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°07'58"	W001°09'02"	229	1
2	N051°55'26"	W000°08'50"	7497	1
3	N051°37'32"	W001°27'13"	1	6012
4	N051°25'10"	W000°27'36"	7269	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOTZ HRVZ 026-248/0 25 MAR 91
P

N50°22' / W003°49' 10"L 11H 35MN 245 N18
BMA07080 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07080

SPOT2 HRV2 028-246/0 13 MAR 93
P

N51°19' / W082°24' 19°R 11H 10MN 09S N1B
BMA08114 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BNA 08114

SPOT1 HRV1 028-247/0 22 MAY 92
P

N50°50' W002°18' 25"L 11H 40MN 50S N18
BMA07081 CCTCONTROL @CNES1992

BMA07081

SPOT2 HRV2 029-241/0 01 DEC 90
P

N53°39' / W001°16' 04"L 11H 27MN 25S N1B
BMA07087 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA07087

SPOT2 HRV2 029-243/0 05 FEB 93
P

N52°43'W001°08' 25°R 11H 02MN 08S N1B
BMA07102 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA07102

SPOT2 HRV2 029-245/0 13 MAR 93
P

N51°47'W002°13' 19°R 11H 10MN 01S N1B
BMA07103 CCTCONTROL 0CNES1993

BMA07103

SPOT2 HRY1 030-242/1 26 NOV 91
P

N53°08'W000°10' 17°R 11H 04MN 39S N1B
BMA07104 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07104

SPOT3 HRV2 030-243/0 14 MAR 94
P

N52°43' / W000°22' 11°L 11H 27MN 07S N1B
BMA07112 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07112

SPOT2 HRV2 030-244/0 26 MAR 94
P

N52°15' W090°41' 24"L 11H 38MN 295 N18
BMA07113 CCTCONTROL @CHES1994

BMA07113

SPOT2 HRV2 030-245/0 13 JUL 90
P

N51°47'W000°49' 25°L 11H 39MN 075 N1B
BMA05682 CCTCONTROL GCNES1990

BMA05682

CD Number : 7000005760
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 15-JUN-1995 08:01:26

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	41	Scene std.	2 030-246 94/03/26 11:38:46 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	42	Scene std.	2 030-247 94/03/26 11:38:54 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	43	Scene std.	2 032-246 91/09/13 11:28:08 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
4	44	Scene std.	2 032-247 91/09/13 11:28:16 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
5	45	Scene std.	2 033-243 91/09/13 11:27:43 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
6	46	Scene std.	2 033-244 94/01/14 11:03:24 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
7	47	Scene std.	3 033-244 94/01/17 11:03:56 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
8	48	Scene std.	3 033-245 94/02/06 11:19:32 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
9	49	Scene std.	2 034-243 90/08/03 11:35:03 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
10	50	Scene std.	3 034-244 94/01/16 11:23:12 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 10

Work order : 9505232641
CD number : 7000005760
Scene ID : 2 30-246 94/03/26 11:38:46 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:52:05

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 30-246 94/03/26 11:38:46 2 P
K-J identification 30-246
Date 94/03/26
Time 11 h 38 mn 46 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 018.1 Degres
Incidence angle L24.8 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +169.4 Elevation: 040.0
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.53899

Number of lines 6013
Number of pixels per line 7418
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'46"
Longitude W001°15'07"
Pixel number 3643
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°39'52"	W001°35'07"	233	1
2	N051°27'44"	W000°36'05"	7418	1
3	N051°09'23"	W001°52'50"	1	6013
4	N050°57'23"	W000°54'23"	7186	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232642
 CD number : 7000005760
 Scene ID : 2 30-247 94/03/26 11:38:54 2 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:53:55

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 30-247 94/03/26 11:38:54 2 P
 K-J identification 30-247
 Date 94/03/26
 Time 11 h 38 mn 54 s
 Instrument HRV2
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 017.9 Degres
 Incidence angle L24.8 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +169.0 Elevation: 040.4
 Gain Number 7
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.53899

Number of lines 6013
 Number of pixels per line 7421
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°50'29"
 Longitude W001°31'41"
 Pixel number 3645
 Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°11'32"	W001°51'35"	237	1
2	N050°59'32"	W000°53'06"	7421	1
3	N050°41'01"	W002°08'59"	1	6013
4	N050°29'09"	W001°11'03"	7185	6013

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6014	6013
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232643
CD number : 7000005760
Scene ID : 2 32-246 91/09/13 11:28:08 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:53:28

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 32-246 91/09/13 11:28:08 1 P
K-J identification 32-246
Date 91/09/13
Time 11 h 28 mn 08 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.5 Degres
Incidence angle L15.4 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +170.1 Elevation: 042.4
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.75707

Number of lines 6011
Number of pixels per line 6663
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'45"
Longitude W000°19'41"
Pixel number 3297
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°38'57"	W000°37'41"	239	1
2	N051°29'02"	E000°15'34"	6663	1
3	N051°08'11"	W000°54'06"	1	6011
4	N050°58'23"	W000°01'23"	6425	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232644
CD number : 7000005760
Scene ID : 2 32-247 91/09/13 11:28:16 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 15:55:51

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 32-247 91/09/13 11:28:16 1 P
K-J identification 32-247
Date 91/09/13
Time 11 h 28 mn 16 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.3 Degres
Incidence angle L15.4 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +169.7 Elevation: 042.9
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.75707

Number of lines 6011
Number of pixels per line 6666
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°50'28"
Longitude W000°34'54"
Pixel number 3298
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°10'37"	W000°52'49"	243	1
2	N051°00'49"	W000°00'03"	6666	1
3	N050°39'50"	W001°08'55"	1	6011
4	N050°30'09"	W000°16'41"	6424	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232645
 CD number : 7000005760
 Scene ID : 2 33-243 91/09/13 11:27:43 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:05:42

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 33-243 91/09/13 11:27:43 1 P
 K-J Identification 33-243
 Date 91/09/13
 Time 11 h 27 mn 43 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 017.1 Degres
 Incidence angle L15.4 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +171.2 Elevation: 041.1
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.75707

Number of lines 6010
 Number of pixels per line 6657
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°43'15"
 Longitude E000°27'36"
 Pixel number 3294
 Line number 3004

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°03'34"	E000°09'19"	231	1
2	N052°53'18"	E001°04'08"	6657	1
3	N052°32'54"	W000°08'03"	1	6010
4	N052°22'46"	E000°46'11"	6427	6010

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6011	6010
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232646
CD number : 7000005760
Scene ID : 2 33-244 94/01/14 11:03:24 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:05:35

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 33-244 94/01/14 11:03:24 1 P
K-J identification 33-244
Date 94/01/14
Time 11 h 03 mn 24 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 012.5 Degres
Incidence angle R11.1 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +164.9 Elevation: 015.3
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.65634

Number of lines 5992
Number of pixels per line 6473
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°15'09"
Longitude E000°45'09"
Pixel number 3260
Line number 2995

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°34'24"	E000°24'58"	259	1
2	N052°27'06"	E001°18'34"	6473	1
3	N052°03'07"	E000°11'39"	1	5992
4	N051°55'54"	E001°04'39"	6215	5992

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5993	5992
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232647
CD number : 7000005760
Scene ID : 3 33-244 94/01/17 11:03:56 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:07:04

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 33-244 94/01/17 11:03:56 1 P
K-J identification 33-244
Date 94/01/17
Time 11 h 03 mn 56 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 012.0 Degres
Incidence angle R14.5 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +164.0 Elevation: 015.7
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.82444

Number of lines 5989
Number of pixels per line 6640
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°14'53"
Longitude E000°01'49"
Pixel number 3351
Line number 2993

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°34'06"	W000°19'28"	259	1
2	N052°26'56"	E000°35'41"	6640	1
3	N052°02'46"	W000°32'16"	1	5989
4	N051°55'40"	E000°22'15"	6382	5989

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5990	5989
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232648
CD number : 7000005760
Scene ID : 3 33-245 94/02/06 11:19:32 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:07:45

S P O T
I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 33-245 94/02/06 11:19:32 1 P
K-J identification 33-245
Date 94/02/06
Time 11 h 19 mn 32 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 015.4 Degres
Incidence angle L07.3 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +166.1 Elevation: 021.4
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.82444

Number of lines 6007
Number of pixels per line 6337
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°46'39"
Longitude E000°12'23"
Pixel number 3152
Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°06'23"	W000°05'14"	241	1
2	N051°57'38"	E000°46'07"	6337	1
3	N051°35'27"	W000°20'49"	1	6007
4	N051°26'48"	E000°30'00"	6097	6007

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6008	6007
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232649
CD number : 7000005760
Scene ID : 2 34-243 90/08/03 11:35:03 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:12:23

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 34-243 90/08/03 11:35:03 2 P
K-J identification 34-243
Date 90/08/03
Time 11 h 35 mn 03 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 019.5 Degres
Incidence angle L28.2 Degres
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +169.5 Elevation: 054.9
Gain Number 6
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.27814

Number of lines 6012
Number of pixels per line 7832
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°42'59"
Longitude E001°25'26"
Pixel number 3835
Line number 3006

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°04'44"	E001°03'56"	221	1
2	N052°50'55"	E002°07'55"	7832	1
3	N052°34'30"	E000°44'33"	1	6012
4	N052°20'52"	E001°47'55"	7612	6012

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6013	6012
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232650
 CD number : 7000005760
 Scene ID : 3 34-244 94/01/16 11:23:12 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 14-JUN-1995 16:13:31

S P O T
 I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 34-244 94/01/16 11:23:12 1 P
 K-J identification 34-244
 Date 94/01/16
 Time 11 h 23 mn 12 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 016.9 Degres
 Incidence angle L15.5 Degres
 Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +169.8 Elevation: 016.4
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.82444

Number of lines 6011
 Number of pixels per line 6669
 Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N052°14'47"
 Longitude E001°08'48"
 Pixel number 3300
 Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N052°35'04"	E000°50'33"	231	1
2	N052°24'54"	E001°44'55"	6669	1
3	N052°04'22"	E000°33'32"	1	6011
4	N051°54'19"	E001°27'20"	6439	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOT2 HRV2 030-246/0 26 MAR 94
P

N51°19'W001°15' 24°L 11H 38MN 46S N1B
BMA07117 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07117

SPOT2 HRV2 030-247/0 26 MAR 94
P

N50°50' / W001°32' 24"L 11H 38MN 54S N1B
BMA07118 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07118

SPOT2 HRV1 032-246/0 13 SEP 91
P

N51°19'W000°20' 15°L 11H 28MN 075 N1B
BMA06236 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA06236

SPOT2 HRV1 032-247/0 13 SEP 91
P

N50°50' W000°35' 15"L 11H 28MN 16S N1B
BMA03920 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA03920

SPOT2 HRV1 033-243/0 13 SEP 91
P

NS2°43' / E000°28' 15°L 11H 27MN 43S N1B
BMA07123 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA07123

SPOT2 HRV1 033-244/0 14 JAN 94
P

N52°15'/E000°45' 11°R 11H 03MN 24S N1B
BMA07124 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07124

SPOT3 HRV1 033-244/0 17 JAN 94
P

NSZ*15//E000*02' 14*R 11H 03MN 56S N1E
BMA07125 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07125

SPOT3 HRY1 033-245/0 06 FEB 94
P

NS1*47'/E000*12' 07*L 11H 19MN 325 N1B
EMA07126 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07126

SPOT2 HRV2 034-243/0 03 AUG 90
P

NS2°43'/E001°25' 28"L 11H 35MN 03S N1B
BMA02363 CCTCONTROL @CNES1990

BMA02363

SPOT3 HRW1 034-244/0 16 JAN 94
P

N52°15' E001°09' 15°L 11H 23MN 12S N1E
BMA07130 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07130

CD Number : 7000005704
Order Number : 95052326
Customer Name : NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE LTD.

S P O T
I M A G E

Date : 8-JUN-1995 11:42:27

CD-ROM Directory

Sequence number	Item	Type	Description
1	53	Scene std.	2 021-242 93/02/14 11:29:09 2 P Level 1B SAT 0
2	51	Scene std.	2 034-246 91/01/07 11:16:17 1 P Level 1B SAT 0
3	52	Scene std.	3 034-247 94/01/16 11:23:36 1 P Level 1B SAT 0

Number of items on CD-ROM : 3

Work order : 9505232653
CD number : 7000005704
Scene ID : 2 21-242 93/02/14 11:29:09 2 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 8-JUN-1995 09:41:59

S P O T

I M A G E

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 21-242 93/02/14 11:29:09 2 P
K-J identification 21-242
Date 93/02/14
Time 11 h 29 mn 09 s
Instrument HRV2
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 012.8 Degrees
Incidence angle R10.7 Degrees
Sun angles (degrees) Azimut: +163.2 Elevation: 022.1
Gain Number 7
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.71424

Number of lines 5993
Number of pixels per line 6454
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N053°11'19"
Longitude W004°39'32"
Pixel number 3249
Line number 2995

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N053°30'36"	W004°59'58"	255	1
2	N053°23'10"	W004°05'24"	6454	1
3	N052°59'22"	W005°13'46"	1	5993
4	N052°52'01"	W004°19'50"	6200	5993

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	5994	5993
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232651
 CD number : 7000005704
 Scene ID : 2 34-246 91/01/07 11:16:17 1 P
 Product Code : TB0200L
 Date : 8-JUN-1995 10:47:01

S P O T
 IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 2 34-246 91/01/07 11:16:17 1 P
 K-J identification 34-246
 Date 91/01/07
 Time 11 h 16 mn 17 s
 Instrument HRV1
 Shift Along Track 0
 Processing level 1B
 Spectral mode PAN
 Number of spectral bands 1
 Spectral band indicators PAN
 Orientation angle 015.2 Degres
 Incidence angle L07.3 Degres
 Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +168.9 Elevation: 015.8
 Gain Number 8
 Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.76453

Number of lines 6007
 Number of pixels per line 6331
 Row of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N051°18'45"
 Longitude E000°54'10"
 Pixel number 3150
 Line number 3003

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°38'27"	E000°36'41"	247	1
2	N051°29'49"	E001°27'28"	6331	1
3	N051°07'29"	E000°21'23"	1	6007
4	N050°58'57"	E001°11'39"	6085	6007

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6008	6007
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

Work order : 9505232652
CD number : 7000005704
Scene ID : 3 34-247 94/01/16 11:23:36 1 P
Product Code : TB0200L
Date : 8-JUN-1995 09:42:12

S P O T

IMAGE

Scene parameters

Scene ID 3 34-247 94/01/16 11:23:36 1 P
K-J identification 34-247
Date 94/01/16
Time 11 h 23 mn 36 s
Instrument HRV1
Shift Along Track 0
Processing level 1B
Spectral mode PAN
Number of spectral bands 1
Spectral band indicators PAN
Orientation angle 016.4 Degres
Incidence angle L15.5 Degres
Sun angles (degres) Azimut: +169.1 Elevation: 017.7
Gain Number 8
Absolute calibration gains (W/m2/sr/um) 01.82444

Number of lines 6011
Number of pixels per line 6674
Raw of the First Image Pixel within the record byte nr 33

Scene Center Location

Latitude N050°50'06"
Longitude E000°22'22"
Pixel number 3302
Line number 3005

Corners Location

Corner	Latitude	Longitude	Pixel n°	Line n°
1	N051°10'17"	E000°04'24"	239	1
2	N051°00'26"	E000°57'15"	6674	1
3	N050°39'29"	W000°11'42"	1	6011
4	N050°29'46"	E000°40'37"	6436	6011

Files parameters

	Record length	Number of records	Number of imagery rec.
Volume directory	360	5	
Leader File	3960	27	
Imagery file	8640	6012	6011
Trailer file	1080	3	
Null volume directory	360	1	

Histogram for spectral band number: 1

SPOTZ HRV2 021-242/0 14 FEB 93
P

N53°11' / W004°40' 10°R 11H 29MN 09S N1B
BMA07137 CCTCONTROL @CNES1993

BMA07137

SPOT2 HRV1 034-246/0 07 JAN 91
P

N51°19' E000°54' 07°L 11H 16MN 17S N1B
BMA06697 CCTCONTROL @CNES1991

BMA06697

SPOT3 HRV1 034-247/0 16 JAN 94
P

N50°50'E000°22' 15"L 11H 23MN 36S N1B
BMA07135 CCTCONTROL @CNES1994

BMA07135